

The Study of Workplace and Work Experiences on Employee Performance

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Abstract. Workplace and work experience are factors can affect to employee performance. To achieve a maximum performance, employees must be supported by a good internal environment and meet comfort standards, in addition the work experience also has an important role in supporting employee performance, the more work experience they have, the better the employee's performance. This study aims to determine the effect of the workplace and work experience on employee performance. This study uses a quantitative method and total sample of this study is 86 respondents. Data analysis using multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the SPSS software. Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis obtained results that partially the workplace and work experience have an influence on employee performance.

Keywords: Workplace, Work Experience, Employee Performance

JEL Code: J5 J6 J8

Introduction

In the current era of globalization, human resources are an important asset in efforts to achieve corporate goals. The survival of a company depends on the extent to which the company takes advantage of opportunities and is able to overcome threats from the environment with all the potential of the resources owned by the company. Without the role of humans even though the various factors needed are available, the organization will not run. Because humans are the drivers and determiners of the way an organization manages its resources effectively and efficiently, quality human resources are needed. One of the factors that influence a company's success rate is employee performance. Employee performance according to Mangkunegara (2013) is the result of quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. In this study, researchers took Indonesian private company, which is one of the companies engaged in the production of salt and operates many employees as movers of the company. In a salt manufacturing company it is needed a good ability of its employees to produce quality products. To produce quality products, affordable prices, and preferred by consumers requires the ability and accuracy in the process of making salt.

Many factors need to be considered to improve employee performance, one of which is work experience. According to Handoko (2014) work experience is the mastery of employees' knowledge and skills measured by the length of work, the level of knowledge and skills possessed by employees. Experience can only be obtained through the workplace. In accordance with the statement of Marwansyah (2014), work experience is very important role in the organization. An employee who has prior work experience will certainly understand more in dealing with a problem that arises, besides that the employee will more quickly adapt to the task at hand because he already has previous work experience, the organization will more easily achieve its goals, because it is supported by employees who are experienced in their respective fields. The experience gained by a person will help in providing knowledge and skills that are appropriate to the work in his field. Someone doing this type of work repeatedly in a long time will make him become more familiar and skilled in carrying out work.

The success of an organization in achieving its goals is inseparable from the factors of the work environment. The company as the work parent must provide a comfortable and conducive work environment so that it is able to lure employees to work conducive. If an employee feels comfortable with the work environment either due to work atmosphere or from the relationship between employees, then the employee will be more confident in doing every job otherwise if the work environment is very adequate then the employee will be more enthusiastic in working, not easily hurt, and more concentration in completing work in accordance with the target.

As a result of preliminary observations, the researchers concluded that the physical environment in PT. Salt (Persero) Surabaya was sufficient to meet the standards but there were some aspects that were not fulfilled. This can be seen when one of the employees said that the limited space in a room disturbed the employee's space. Besides that, the work space in one of the less than ideal areas can be seen by the fact that the head of subdivision is still united with the staff section. This makes employees feel that the work process is very monotonous because they feel very monitored by their superiors. With this atmosphere makes employees feel bored quickly and get tired easily at work. In addition, the management of the existing archives is not properly organized so that a lot of files are scattered in the workplace of each employee which can cause work to be disrupted and very messy. However, other physical environments such as lighting or light are in accordance with NAV, air circulation has met this standard, it appears that there is already air conditioning in every room so that the stuffy felt by employees due to limited space is minimized by adequate room temperature.

Based on the description above, the authors are interested in conducting research to find out whether the work environment and work experience affect the performance of employees of PT. Salt (Persero) Surabaya either partially or simultaneously and to know the Which of these two variables ya ng dominant influence.

Literature Review

Employee performance

Performance is something that is individual, because every employee has a different level of ability to do their jobs. Performance depends on a combination of ability, effort, and opportunity that is gained. Performance comes from job performance or actual performance which means the actual achievements of a person (Masram and Mu'ah, 2017). When associated with performance as a noun (noun), then the notion of performance or performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with authority and responsibility. According to Pasolong (2010) the factors that influence employee performance are as follows:

1. Ability, is an ability in a field that is influenced by adequate talent, intelligence (intelligence) and interest.
2. Willingness, which is a willingness to spend a high level of effort for organizational goals.
3. Energy, which is a source of strength from within oneself. With the energy, a person is able to respond and react to whatever is needed, without thinking long or conscious attention so that the mental acuity and concentration in managing work becomes higher.
4. Technology, which is the application of existing knowledge to facilitate the work.
5. Compensation, which is something that is received by employees as a reward for performance and benefit him.
6. Clarity of purpose, namely the goal that must be achieved by employees. This goal must be clear so that the work carried out by employees can be directed and run more effectively and efficiently.
7. Security, which is a fundamental human need, because in general someone who feels safe in doing his work, will affect his performance.

The Workplace

Understanding the work environment according to Sunyoto (2013) is everything that is around the workers and that can affect him in carrying out the tasks that are charged, such as cleanliness, music, lighting and others. If a business wants to grow, develop and offer high-quality products and services, it must create a work environment where everyone wants to do the best they can (ILO, 2013).. The work environment itself has two dimensions, namely the physical work environment which consists of the state of the room, lighting, cleanliness, room layout and others. While the non-physical work environment which leads to the welfare of employees, work atmosphere, relations between superiors and employees and relationships between colleagues work. The company must be able to provide both dimensions in good condition so as to enable employees to continue working productively and cooperate with employees and leaders to achieve company goals. The work environment is said to be good if humans in it can carry out activities optimally and safely (Moulana, F. et al., 2017)

Work Experience

Work experience in similar work, needs to get consideration in the placement of workers. The reality shows that the longer the workforce works, the more experience the relevant workforce has. Conversely, the shorter the work period, the less experience is gained. A lot of work experience provides expertise and work skills. Conversely, limited work experience results in lower levels of expertise and skills. The ability to complete tasks is not determined by one's intelligence, but rather the experience of someone, failure and success of someone will determine the actions in the future (Rahmawati, NH, 2016). People who have experience in working better than people who are new to the work, as much to learn from previous pekerjaan, pengalaman worked very useful in supporting a person's future career will come (Sofian, E. and Julkarnain, 2019). Work experience shows the ability to work in previous places and describes the length of work (Kumeang, NC et al., 2019)

Framework

Figure 1. Framework for Thinking

Hypothesis

H1 : The workplace affects the performance of the employees of Indonesian private company.

H2 : The work experience affects the performance of employees of Indonesian private company.

H3 : It is suspected that the workplace and work experience simultaneously influence (together) the employees of the employees of Indonesian private company.

H4 : It is suspected that the workplace has a dominant effect on the performance of Indonesian private company

Method

Object of research

The object of this research was carried out at PT. Salt (Persero) Surabaya.

Types of research

The type of research the writer uses is quantitative research methods.

Population and Sample

The population in this study is employees of Indonesian private company, amounting to 604 samples. The sampling technique used in this study is simple random sampling. The number of samples used in this study were 86 respondents through the Slovin formula

Data source

Primary data p there this study was obtained from questionnaires were distributed and filled by the respondent which contains questions about the problems studied, while the secondary data obtained by researchers from the literature, previous research, and journals related to the topic.

Data collection method

In this study, data collection tools used by researchers as follows: questionnaire and documentation.

Data analysis method

The data obtained before it is served in the form of information will dioalah and analyzed using SPSS software 20. Analyze d igunakan is a previous multiple regression analysis to test the validity, test reliability, Classical Assumption Test, test keefisien determination, and testing hypotheses.

Discussion

Validity test

Test the Validity of Workplace Variables

Table 1. Test Results of Validity of Workplace Variables

Statement Items	r count	r table	Information
X 1.1	0.791	0.1786	Valid
X 1.2	0.654	0.1786	Valid
X 1.3	.627	0.1786	Valid
X 1.4	.751	0.1786	Valid
X 1.5	.691	0.1786	Valid
X 1.6	0.638	0.1786	Valid
X 1.7	0.664	0.1786	Valid
X 1.8	.682	0.1786	Valid
X 1.9	0.680	0.1786	Valid
X 1.10	0.786	0.1786	Valid

The results of the correlation value of each statement item has a value of $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$. Thus based on the validity test shows that all items statement on workplace variables are declared valid and can be used as research instruments.

Test the Validity of Work Experience Variables

Table 2. Results of Test Validity of Work Experience Variables

Statement Items	r count	r table	Information
X 2.1	0.659	0.1786	Valid
X 2.2	0.662	0.1786	Valid
X 2.3	.753	0.1786	Valid
X 2.4	0.760	0.1786	Valid
X 2.5	.696	0.1786	Valid
X 2.6	0.685	0.1786	Valid

The results of the correlation value of each statement item has a value of $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$. Thus based on the validity test shows that on all items a statement on the work experience variable is declared valid and can be used as research instruments.

Test the Validity of Employee Performance Variables

Table 3. Results of the Validity Test of Employee Performance Variables

Statement Items	r count	r table	Information
Y 1.1	0.616	0.1786	Valid
Y 1.2	0.670	0.1786	Valid
Y 1.3	0.818	0.1786	Valid
Y 1.4	0.820	0.1786	Valid
Y 1.5	0.822	0.1786	Valid
Y 1.6	0.699	0.1786	Valid

The results of the correlation value of each statement item has a value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$. Thus based on the validity test shows that all statement items on employee performance variables are declared valid and can be used as research instruments.

Reliability Test

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Criteria	Information
Workplace (X_1)	.776	0.60	Reliable
Work experience (X_2)	0.732	0.60	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	.802	0.60	Reliable

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the Cronbach's Alpha value of the workplace variable (X_1), work experience variable (X_2) and employee performance variable (Y) results of $\text{Nilai cronbach alpha} > 0.60$. Thus it can be concluded that, the statement of the questionnaire has been reliable which means that this questionnaire can be used in research.

Classical Assumption Testing
 Normality test

Figure 2. Normality Test

In the picture the normality test results can be seen that the data points spread around the diagonal line and the direction of the spread follows the diagonal line so that the regression model meets the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
1 Work_Internal_Environment	.684	1,463
Employee_Experience	.684	1,463

In the table above, regarding the multicollinearity test results using VIF, it appears that the workplace variable has a tolerance value of 0.684 and a variance inflation factor (VIF) of 1,463. Work experience variable has a tolerance value of 0.684 and variance inflation factor (VIF) of 1,463. From the multicollinearity test results there are no variables that have a tolerance value below 0.10 and a

variance inflation factor (VIF) value above 10. It can be concluded that this research does not occur multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Figure 3. Heteroskedasticity Test Results

In the picture above, it can be seen that there is no specific pattern and the data points spread below and above the number 0 (zero), so that the regression model is not affected by symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Determination Coefficient Test

Table 6. Calculation Results for Coefficient Test R and R

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.851 ^a	.724	.718	.22298	1,969

From the table based on the test results the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.724, it shows 72.4% of employee performance is explained by workplace variables and work experience. While the remaining 27.6% is explained by other variables not explained in this study.

Hypothesis testing

T test (partial)

Table 7. Calculation of the T Test at the Significant Level 0.1

Model	T	Sig.
(Constant)	2.265	.026
1 Work_Internal_Environment	7.117	.000
Work experience	6.702	.000

Based on the results of the t test presented in the table above, it shows that workplace and work experience variables affect employee performance.

Workplace

Hypothesis

H0: $\beta_1 = 0$, Lingkungan internal work does not affect the performance of employees.

H1: $\beta_1 \neq 0$, Lingkungan internal workings of influence on employee performance.

Workplace variable T value of 7.117 and the significance level of 0.000 is smaller than 0.1 so it shows the results that the workplace has an effect on employee performance.

Work experience

Hypothesis

H0: $\beta_2 = 0$, work experience has no effect on employee performance.

H1: $\beta_2 \neq 0$, work experience influences employee performance.

Variable work experience has a calculated T value of 6.702 and a significance level of 0.000 less than 0.1 so that shows the results that work experience has an effect on employee performance.

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

Table 7. Calculation of F Test at Significant Levels 0.1

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	10851	2	5,426	109,127	.000 ^b
Residual	4,127	83	.50		
Total	14,978	85			

Hypothesis

H0: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0$, work experience has no effect on employee performance

H1: $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq 0$, workplace and work experience has no effect on employee performance

Based on the above table, the results of the simultaneous test show that the value of Fcount 109.127 is greater than Ftable. N use values sig. Based on the results of the F statistical test of 0,000 less than 0.1, this shows that the work environment and work experience variables were jointly tested to affect employee performance.

Hypothesis Determination of Variables that Influence Dominant

Table 8. Beta Coefficient Values

Model	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta		
(Constant)		2,265	.026
1 Work_Internal_Environment	.496	7117	.000
Work experience	.467	6,702	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee_Performance

Based on the table above shows that the value of Standardized Coefficient Beta workplace variable is 0.496 which is higher than the work experience variable of 0.467 so that ($0.496 > 0.467$). Then it can be concluded that the workplace variables have a more dominant influence on the employee performance variables of Indonesian private company. From these results it can be stated that H4 is accepted and H0 is rejected.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 9. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	Unstandardize d Coefficients Beta (B)	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t count	Sig	Information
Constant	607		2,265	.026	Significant

Workplace (X ₁)	.634	496	7117	.000	Significant
Work Experience (X ₂)	.536	.467	6,702	.000	Significant
R				.851 ^a	
Adjusted R Square				.718	
F count				109,127	
Sig. F				.000 ^b	
A				0.1	
Information					
The amount of data				86	
Variable Dependent				Employee performance	

The results of the multiple regression analysis table obtained the regression equation, namely:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2$$

$$Y = 0.607 + 0,634X_1 + 0,536X_2$$

Based on the regression equation above it can be concluded as follows:

1. Constant value = 0.607

The constant value of 0.607 indicates that if the independent variable X₁, X₂ is in a constant or constant condition, then the value of the employee's performance is Indonesian private company (Y) of 0.607 units

2. Value of β₁ = 0.634

A value of β₁ indicates a value of 0.634 and has a positive regression coefficient sign. This means that if the workplace variable (X₁) increases by 1 unit, the employee's performance is Indonesian private company (Y) will experience an increase of 0.634 units. Assuming the variable X₂ is in a constant or constant condition.

3. Value of β₂ = 0.536

A β₂ value indicates a value of 0.536 and has a positive regression coefficient sign. This means that if the work experience variable (X₂) increases by 1 unit, the performance of the employees of Indonesian private company (Y) will experience an increase of 0.536 units. Assuming variable X₁ is in a constant or constant condition.

Discussion

Work Environment Indicator

The first indicator of the workplace is lighting or light at work. The results of the questionnaire showed that 57% agreed and 41% strongly agreed. Lighting and lighting in Indonesian private company (Persero) already meet the standard, pencaha O's with color lights that do not build an eyesight sick despite being indoors within watu long enough, so that it affects the performance of employees, with good lighting, the employee comfortable at work.

The second indicator of air circulation in the workplace, 36 strongly agreed and 48 respondents strongly agreed. This is indicated by the air circulation in every work space in Indonesian private company has been installed properly, each room has been installed air-conditioning but that does not make every room closed, there are still windows with standard sizes that can be opened and closed to adjust the desires of employees, and there are ventilation holes for air to get in and out, so that if the AC is turned off, the air can come in outside so it doesn't make the room stuffy.

The third indicator of workplace decoration, the choice of color from the workspace becomes an important point for employees because the choice of room color will affect the mood of the employee. In Indonesian private company the room color selection is light blue, this color is a bright and soft color that makes the viewing eye become comfortable and then affects the mood that helps to be calm. This was agreed by 56% of employees and 41% said strongly agree, so that the selection of

light blue in the room makes employees more calm and comfortable in completing work. In this third indicator there is also a good and correct work desk arrangement, in this section the work space arrangement in Indonesian private company still needs to be re-considered because the positions between the employee desks are still too close, empty barriers are only enough for one person to walk, so it needs to be rearranged by reducing the number of tables in each room so that it is more organized and more comfortable for employees. The fourth indicator is odors at work, at Indonesian private company showing this indicator as a problem that is still a small obstacle to employee performance. Trash cans that are placed in air-conditioned rooms then cause unpleasant odors because employees also throw food waste into them, and if the cleaners are late doing a little garbage disposal then it makes the odor less unpleasant and disrupts the performance of employees, but things it does not become a significant problem, meaning that in this indicator odor problems do not occur very often.

The last indicator is security in the workplace, to minimize the crime that occurred at Indonesian private company in every corner of the room has a CCTV that is guarded 24 hours non-stop by security officers. The company has set security standards well with the number of security officers on duty in turn, and conduct checks on every guest who visits Indonesian private company, therefore this becomes comfortable in working.

Indicators Oversight LongWorking

The first indicator in a long working experience of work or employment, the longer the employee works at Indonesian private company will be more and more experience of an employment obtained, so that employees can master both tasks - the tasks assigned to the employee. Employees who have long worked have good tricks and timeliness in completing existing tasks, this was agreed by 44% of respondents, and 52% expressed strongly agree.

The second indicator that the level of knowledge, in this indicator of employee knowledge not only about learning that employees can at the time of formal education, but also the education's employees of various skills in can be either self-taught or from their jobs before working at Indonesian private company.

Employees who have a high level of knowledge certainly have initiative and innovation in doing work, and with extensive knowledge they can adapt and master the work well and are responsible for the positions they occupy. This is as much as 45% states strongly agree and 53% agree.

The third indicator is mastery of work, this relates to mastery of work support tools and also the skills possessed by employees in operating work equipment. At Indonesian private company (Persero) 47 respondents stated that they agreed and 37 respondents strongly agreed that indicators of occupational control were the determinants of their performance.

The Effect of Workplace on Employee Performance

Hypothesis test results indicate that the workplace affects the performance of employees of Indonesian private company. This shows that the better the internal working environment in Indonesian private company (Per sero), the better the employee's performance. Conversely, if the worse circumstances intrernal work environment in the company, which it will lower the performance of employees in the company. because with a comfortable environment can make employees work well, so they can improve good performance for the company. The above results support the research that dialakukan by Permanasari, R. (2013) show that the working environment air- influence on employee performance. The results of the same were also obtained from the research that is done by Potu, A. (2013) showed that the work environment influence on employee performance.

The Effect of Work Experience on Employee Performance

variable work experience variables affect the performance of employees of Indonesian private company. Work experience is an ability that is obtained along with the work period that has been taken by someone who can understand the tasks of a job and carried out properly. The length of time a person becomes an employee will determine his experience in working. The longer a person works, the more experienced they will be in solving problems in the field of work. In other words, the higher the work experiences that employees, then it will be better performance. Likewise, the lower that employees have work experience, it will get worse anyway performance. The above research results support the results of research conducted by Aristarini, L. et al. (2014) showed that experience

working positive and significant influence on employee performance. Similar results were obtained from studies conducted by Wirawan, KE et al (2019) showed that experience work affects the performance of employees.

The Influence of Workplace and Work Experience on Employee Performance

The results of simultaneous testing (together) which shows that there is a positive and significant influence between the work environment variables and work experience on employee performance. This means that with the improvement level will conscious work environment and work experience will improve the performance of employees so that the objectives of the company can be reached.

Conclusion

1. The workplace influences the performance of the employees of Indonesian private company. This is indicated by the highest score of respondents agreeing and strongly agreeing to the indicator of lighting or lighting in the workspace, air circulation at work, decoration at work, and safety at work.
2. Work experience affects the performance of employees of Indonesian private company. This is indicated by the respondents chose agree and strongly agree bahwa length of employment or employment has a positive influence on employee performance, and indicators of the level of education has a positive influence on employee performance, then the respondents also said they agree and strongly agree that mastery of the job have an influence positive for employee performance.
3. Workplace and work experience have a simultaneous effect (together) on the performance of the employees of Indonesian private company. This can be seen from the F-count value of 109.127 > F-table of 3.11.
4. The results of testing the dominant variable, the workplace variable has the highest Beta value of 0.496 and it is proven that the workplace variable has a dominant effect on the performance of the employees of Indonesian private company.

From all the hypotheses presented in the previous chapter, it is known that all hypotheses are acceptable.

Suggestion

1. On the influence of the workplace there are odor indicators contained in the workspace, in this indicator the employee states this is a problem, although it does not happen often but this interferes with the employee's performance because the trash is in the work space and there is food waste then this creates an unpleasant odor if the janitor does not immediately remove it from the room. This should be a concern of Indonesian private company to emphasize more to employees not to throw food waste in the workspace, and emphasize discipline for official staff to always be on time and regularly remove waste from the employee workspace.
2. Efforts should be made to consider the suitability of the employee's position or position. Indicators in work experience are positions or positions that are tailored to the expertise or skills possessed by employees, will make employees work wholeheartedly, otherwise when employees feel unhappy they will feel like working under pressure.
3. It is necessary to assess employee performance including quantity, quality and timeliness continuously or regularly so that employee performance can be known so that efforts can be made to improve if there is a decrease in employee performance, one of which is to intensify interaction and communication between employees and between employees and leaders so as to create cooperation and a conducive atmosphere that can support the comfort of the environment to work so as to foster a sense of belonging to the organization. Continue to pay attention to employees by more disciplining employees, paying attention to their responsibilities and attitudes while working
4. Further research needs to be done about the factors that affect employee performance in addition to the factors that have been examined in this study.

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